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ANALYSIS OF ENTROPY NOISE GENERATION AND PROPAGATION IN TURBINE INLET AND BLADE ROW

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ABSTRACT

Stringent emissions regulations as well as improvements to the main sources of turbomachinery and general aircraft noise are driving research on the analysis and optimisation of previously insignificant noise sources. Combustion noise is of particular interest, and it is decomposed into a component generated by the unsteady volume expansion at the heat source (*direct noise*) and the acceleration of entropy, vorticity and compositional inhomogeneities (*indirect noise*) through the turbine. In this paper, the generation and propagation of *entropy noise*, the component of the indirect noise generated by the acceleration of entropy disturbances, in the turbine duct and blade row geometry is investigated using computational aeroacoustics. A distinctive, 2D, high-order, characteristics-based solver with fully non-linear, linearized and adjoint capabilities is introduced and modified, making it compatible for studying the generation and propagation of entropy noise for representative turbomachinery flows. A numerically consistent 1D model is shown to have good entropy noise prediction characteristics, and the results are shown to compare well to the established case of the Entropy Wave Generator experiment. Preliminary results are calculated, and brief observations made on the interactions of the entropy noise with the trailing edge vortex shedding.

INTRODUCTION

Increasingly stringent regulations are placing significant pressures on the aviation industry to improve performance while simultaneously reducing emissions [1].

Despite much having been done to reduce the impact of aircraft noise, some of the noise sources, that have in the past been less researched, are becoming more prominent. Of these, combustion noise, which consists of pressure perturbations due to unsteady volume expansion (*direct noise*) and the acceleration of entropy, vorticity and compositional inhomogeneities (*indirect noise*), is of particular interest. Indeed, efforts to develop the more sensitive lean combustor technology in aero engines are, in part, driving this research [2]. The particular component of indirect noise generated by the acceleration and interaction of entropy waves with turbine geometries is termed *entropy noise*.

Generation and propagation are two aspects of acoustic problems typically dealt with using different methods. This is in part due to somewhat different modelling requirements for the numerical scheme. In the case of entropy noise and non-linear aeroacoustics, these are interrelated and must be dealt with under one unified model. Traditional approaches to entropy noise problems have focused on reduced order models (e.g. [3]), models within linearized frameworks (e.g. [4]) or by decoupling the non-linear generation process at the blade rows from the linear propagation through the rest of the geometry (e.g. [5]). Despite many significant achievements in using these techniques, the coupling between the generation and propagation is an aspect that is often overlooked. As such, the understanding of entropy noise within full geometries is incomplete. Though a limited number of studies have modelled complete rotor-stator configurations using conventional, typically 2nd/3rd-order accurate codes (e.g. [6], [7]), and interactions between the

trailing edge vortex shedding and incoming entropy waves were observed, no detailed analysis of these was performed.

The rarity of unified codes that model both generation and propagation of acoustic waves is due to the need to capture both small perturbations in the acoustics field and large scale variations in the flow field. Many commercial codes making use of low-order schemes are ill-suited to this task, since, with the high numerical dissipation, the acoustics field is quickly dissipated. For this reason, high order CFD and Computational Aeroacoustics (CAA) codes must be used. Such implementations are specifically designed to propagate disturbances at a wide range of frequencies and amplitudes with minimal dissipation.

In this work a high order CAA code, that is able to model high-velocity compressible flows in turbine-duct geometries, with fully non-linear, linearized and adjoint functionality is presented and adapted to the combined problem of entropy noise generation and propagation.

A numerically consistent 1D solver is used as the initial starting point to guide the investigation, providing a reference for subsequent studies within the duct-NGV geometry. Validations against experimental data from the Entropy Wave Generator (EWG) are also obtained and a parametric analysis is performed that illustrates the importance of downstream reflections to the entropy noise signature.

Preliminary results and a brief analysis are given that serve to illustrate the feasibility of predicting and analysing entropy noise within the geometries and configurations of interest.

NOMENCLATURE

p	Pressure
ρ	Density
s	Entropy
\mathbf{u}	Velocity
\mathbf{f}_v	Volume forcing vector
Q_r	Heat source
\mathbf{q}	Heat flux vector
χ	Thermal conductivity
a	Speed of sound
T	Temperature
R	Ideal gas constant
γ	Ratio of specific heats
M	Mach number
Re	Reynolds number (based on aerofoil chord).
Pr	Prandtl number
μ	Viscosity
μ_v	Volume viscosity
ξ^n	Curvilinear basis for the transformation to grid coordinates.
ω	Angular frequency
h	Duct height
u_{99}	99% of freestream velocity

y_{99}	Height of layer next to a non-slip boundary, where $u < u_{99}$
σ	Boundary condition relaxation parameter
η_{β}^{α}	Relaxation parameters for the 2D boundary conditions.
L	Characteristic length scale
W_s	Sponge layer width
R_0	Start point of the sponge layer
t_s	Start time of temperature pulse
ζ	Time dependence of EWG entropy source profile
ψ	Spatial dependence of EWG source
Φ_0	EWG source strength
τ	Relaxation time for the source.
κ	Width control parameter for the source
x_0	Reference length scale
p_0	Reference pressure
ρ_0	Reference density
μ_0	Reference viscosity
k_0	Reference thermal conductivity.
M_{exit}	Exit Mach number
C_p	Pressure coefficient
M_{exit}	Exit Mach number
f_{vs}	Vortex-shedding frequency
f_{source}	Entropy source frequency

UNSTEADY FLOW SOLVER

In contrast to commonly available, conventional CFD solvers, for this study a fully non-linear, high-order, time-domain and pseudo-characteristics-based solver is utilised [8]. A Fifth-order upwinding, compact differencing scheme with tuned high wavenumber damping characteristics (CULD5 [9]), along with fourth-order Runge-Kutta time stepping ensures that the fluctuations in the macro-scale flow quantities and the acoustics field are captured and propagated with minimal numerical losses and distortion.

It is known that following the generation of entropy waves at the combustor, the contraction in the duct area upstream of the nozzle guide vanes would accelerate those waves and generate entropy noise, making it necessary to account for this area change. An obvious approach is to render this model in 3D with non-slip boundary walls in the z-direction modelling the reduction in streamtube height. Although simple, this procedure would incur significant

computational penalties as the number of variables is increased. Moreover, the duct area is constant beyond the leading edge of the NGV, meaning that these additional variables are not required to recover the flow.

Consequently, this solver models the 2D depth-averaged Navier-Stokes equations:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = -\rho \mathbf{u} \cdot \frac{\nabla h}{h}, \quad (1)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \right) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \mathbf{f}_v, \quad (2)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial e}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla e \right) = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} - (\mathbf{q} + p\mathbf{u}) \cdot \frac{\nabla h}{h} + \boldsymbol{\tau} : \nabla \mathbf{u} - p(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) + (Q_r - \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{f}_v), \quad (3)$$

where h is the streamtube height in the z -direction, that is assumed to vary smoothly as a function of the axial coordinate x . The boundaries of the stream-tube are assumed to have an impermeably, zero heat flux and non-slip conditions, a procedure motivated by the method used for deriving the 1D isentropic duct equations.

The form of the viscous tensor $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and heat flux \mathbf{q} are given by

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = \mu(\nabla \mathbf{u} + \nabla \mathbf{u}^t) + \left(\mu_v - \frac{2}{3}\mu \right) (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) \mathbf{I}, \quad (4)$$

and Fourier's law

$$\mathbf{q} = -\chi \nabla T, \quad (5)$$

together with the equations for a calorically perfect gas

$$p = \rho RT \text{ and } e = \frac{R}{\gamma-1} T. \quad (6)$$

Here μ is the viscosity, μ_v is the volume viscosity, χ is the heat conductivity, R is the gas constant and γ is the ratio of specific heats.

Pseudo-characteristics in the description above refer to the fact that the inviscid part of the compressible Navier-Stokes equations may be decomposed into a set of transport terms, with transport speed information derived explicitly for each wave. Such a decomposition is not unique, though a projection onto the grid lines provides practical advantages with regards to the selection of the correct upwinding direction, based upon the direction of propagation of each pseudo-wave. In a 2D setting, these amount to four acoustic pseudo-waves, two entropy pseudo-waves and two cross-transport terms.

In the discussion that follows, all the quoted variables are assumed to be non-dimensional, with the non-dimensionalisation defined below.

$$x' = \frac{x}{x_0}, \quad t' = \frac{u_0 t}{x_0}, \quad u' = \frac{u}{u_0}, \quad p' = \frac{p}{p_0}, \quad s' = \frac{s}{R}, \quad (7)$$

$$\rho' = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0}, \quad \mu' = \frac{\mu}{\mu_0}, \quad k' = \frac{k}{k_0}, \quad \text{and} \quad f' = \frac{x_0 f}{u_0}, \quad (8)$$

and, dropping the primes from the quantities, the non-dimensional relations are given by

$$p = \rho T \quad (\gamma - 1)s = \log \left(\frac{p}{\rho^\gamma} \right) \quad a^2 = \frac{p}{\rho} \quad (9)$$

$$Re = \frac{\rho_0 u_0 x_0}{\mu_0} \quad Pr = \frac{\gamma R}{\gamma - 1} \frac{\mu_0}{k_0} \quad M = \frac{u_0}{a_0} \quad (10)$$

The reference parameters for this non-dimensionalisation are defined at a fixed point in the flow, such as at the outlet boundary.

Pressure and entropy equations are derived using the fundamental thermodynamic identity $de = Tds - pd(1/\rho)$, making use of $a^2 = \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \rho} \right)_s$:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla p = -\rho a^2 \left(\mathbf{u} \cdot \frac{\nabla h}{h} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} \right) + (\gamma - 1)\rho T \left(\frac{\partial s}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla s \right), \quad (11)$$

and

$$\rho T \left(\frac{\partial s}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla s \right) = \boldsymbol{\tau} : \nabla \mathbf{u} - \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} - \mathbf{q} \cdot \frac{\nabla h}{h} + Q_r. \quad (12)$$

Following [10] (details omitted), and projecting these equations onto the curvilinear basis $\boldsymbol{\xi}^k$, the pseudo-characteristics formulation is obtained.

Pressure equation:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \gamma \rho a \sum_l \frac{\theta_l^+ + \theta_l^-}{2} = (\gamma - 1)p \text{RHS}_s - \frac{\gamma p}{h} k^{li} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \xi^l}, \quad (13)$$

Momentum equation:

$$\frac{\partial u^k}{\partial t} + \sum_l \frac{\theta_{(l)}^+ - \theta_{(l)}^-}{2M} \frac{g^{(l)k}}{h^{(l)}} + \sum_l \theta^{kl} = \text{RHS}^k, \quad (14)$$

Entropy equation:

$$\frac{\partial s}{\partial t} + \sum_l \theta_s^l = \text{RHS}_s. \quad (15)$$

The pseudo-waves are defined as:

Acoustic pseudo-waves:

$$\theta_k^\pm = \left(u^{(k)} \pm \frac{a}{M} h^{(k)} \right) \left(\frac{1}{\gamma \rho a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \xi^{(k)}} \pm M \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial \xi^{(k)}} \frac{k^{(k)i}}{h^k} \right), \quad (16)$$

Cross-transport terms:

$$\theta^{kl} = u^{(l)} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial \xi^{(l)}} \left(k^{ki} - k^{(l)i} \frac{g^{k(l)}}{g^{(l)l}} \right), \quad (17)$$

Entropy pseudo-waves:

$$\theta_s^k = u^{(k)} \frac{\partial s}{\partial \xi^{(k)}}, \quad (18)$$

with the shorthands

$$\text{RHS}^k = \frac{1}{Re} \frac{1}{\rho} k^{ki} \frac{\partial \tau_{ji}}{\partial \xi^l} k^{li} + \frac{1}{\rho k^{ki}} f_{vi}, \quad (19)$$

$$\text{RHS}_s = \frac{1}{\rho T} \frac{\gamma M^2}{Re} \tau_{ji} \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial \xi^l} k^{lj} - \frac{\gamma}{\rho T (\gamma - 1) Re Pr} \left[\frac{\partial q_i}{\partial \xi^l} k^{li} + \frac{k^{li} q_i}{h} \frac{\partial h}{\partial \xi^l} + Q_v \right], \quad (20)$$

$$q_i = -\chi \frac{\partial T}{\partial \xi^l k^{li}}, \quad (21)$$

and

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial \xi^l} k^{lj} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial \xi^l} k^{li} \right) + \left(\mu_v - \frac{2}{3}\mu \right) \frac{\partial u_m}{\partial \xi^l} k^{lm} \delta_{ij}. \quad (22)$$

Validations were performed in 2D Cartesian domains with straight and slowly-varying geometric area changes induced by angled, non-slip walls. Isentropic nozzle solutions were recovered accurately for all tested duct profiles.

Time-domain linearization and adjoint functionality are implemented using the procedure detailed in [11], with self-adjoint Krylov subspace methods [12] used to advance the linear and adjoint systems in time.

The code is modular and parallelised using the Message Passing Interface (MPI) library, for efficient parallel computation, and operator extraction may be performed by means of the Portable Extensible Toolkit for Scientific Computation (PETSc) interface.

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS AND SOURCES

A practical application of the pseudo-wave design is that boundary conditions on orthogonal grids may be defined by simple manipulations of the characteristic pseudo-waves at the required interface. The subsequent discussion focuses on the far-field boundaries, as the adaptation of these are of particular relevance here.

The modelling of open flows requires the truncation of the domain in order to restrict the computational effort to specific regions of interest. As such, partially non-reflecting boundary conditions, inspired by the Navier-Stokes Characteristic Boundary Conditions (NSCBCs) described by Poinot and Lele with modifications by Lodato ([13], [14]), are used. These allow incident perturbations with short time scales to leave the domain with reduced levels of reflection, while maintaining a long time-scale value by means of a restoring term and a relaxation factor, analogous to a low-pass filter. In curvilinear coordinates, the incoming information is given by Equation 23 for the acoustic pseudo-wave, Equation 24 for the entropy pseudo-wave and Equation 25 for the cross transport terms. An additional viscous boundary condition must also be imposed to ensure numerical stability, and is given by Equation 25.

$$\Theta_{\pm}^n = \pm \frac{\eta_{\pm}^n}{L} (1 - M^2) \left(\frac{a}{h^n} \right) (u^n - u_{ref}^n) + \text{RHS}_{\pm}^n, \quad (23)$$

$$\Theta_s^n = \frac{\eta_s^n}{L} \left(\frac{a}{M} \right) (s - s_{ref}) + \text{RHS}_s^n, \quad (24)$$

$$\Theta^{tn} = \frac{\eta^t}{L} \left(\frac{a}{M} \right) (u^t - u_{ref}^t) + \text{RHS}^{tn}, \quad (25)$$

$$k^{ni} \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial \xi^n} k^{nj} = 0. \quad (25)$$

The incoming characteristic at the outflow satisfies Equation 11, with viscous conditions as in Equation 12.

$$\Theta_{\pm}^n = \frac{\sigma (1 - M^2) p - 1}{L \gamma M} \frac{p - 1}{\rho} + (1 - \beta) \text{RHS}_k^{\pm} + \beta \text{RHS}_{k, ref}^{\pm} \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{\partial q_n}{\partial \xi^n} = 0, \text{ and } \frac{\partial \tau_{tn}}{\partial \xi^n} = 0. \quad (27)$$

A fundamental requirement is the need to introduce pressure and entropy disturbances into the flow field. Though it may be tempting to introduce these for the

incoming characteristics at the inflow and outflow boundaries, such an approach is undesirable and restrictive. One must ensure that spurious acoustic reflections from the NSCBCs do not contaminate the solution within the interior of the domain, since it is possible that excitation of the outflow boundary due to strong vortical flow could introduce unphysical acoustic feedback. To remedy this, sponge layers [15] with tuneable damping coefficients, $\alpha(\mathbf{x})$, are applied in front of both the inflow and outflow boundaries. These consist of a spatially-dependent forcing term, $-\alpha(\mathbf{x})(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}_{ref})$, that gradually reduces the amplitude of the outgoing disturbance towards a reference state \mathbf{v}_{ref} , and in so doing significantly reduces the magnitude of the reflected wave. In this work, $\alpha(\mathbf{x})$ is given by an exponential form in Equation 13, where a is a tuneable parameter for the layer strength. From the analysis of the pressure time traces in the 2D simulations, it was determined that a sponge layer strength of $a = 5$ provided the best performance for the cases considered.

$$\alpha(\mathbf{x}) = a \left(1 - e^{-\frac{W_s}{x-R_0-W_s} - \frac{W_s}{x-R_0}} \right) \quad (28)$$

A side effect of such a boundary treatment is that any forcing defined at the computational boundary is within this layer, and so is damped before it enters the model domain, which means that sources must be specified within the region between the two sponges. The advantage of the characteristics-based nature of this solver, is that it is possible to perturb the individual pseudo-characteristics, flow variables and/or specify external forcing, such as heat sources, at any location within the domain, and examples of this implementation are provided in the 2D results section.

MESHING

The solver models the full Navier-Stokes system directly, and so it is necessary to resolve the thinnest part of the boundary layer to ensure stability of the numerical solution. A reasonable estimate for this grid spacing is to have approximately 30 vertical nodes within the layer $0 \leq y \leq y_{99}$, where y_{99} is defined as the distance above a viscous wall where $u = 0.99u_{\infty}$.

At present, the solver is limited by a single-block design that requires a single mesh to be generated within the entire computational domain. Though elliptic grid generators (EGG) produce desirable meshes from the smoothness point of view, they are entirely determined by the distribution of points along the boundary, and fine control of grid spacing normal to the boundary is not possible. This is sufficient when the difference between inlet and outlet flow angle is small, or when the aerofoil is thin, with a sharp trailing edge. For more realistic turbine geometries, this becomes a limitation.

To remedy this, it was decided that a thin mesh would be generated, using a hyperbolic grid generator (HGG) [16], outwards from the edges where the non-slip boundary conditions are applied. The interior of the domain is then filled with an elliptic mesh, using the outer edge of the hyperbolic mesh as the new boundary condition.

Using an HGG method to generate a thin mesh at the boundary has the following advantages:

- *fine control of boundary-normal grid spacing:* achieved by controlling the marching step size for the grid generating equations
- *control over grid singularities and curvature:* achieved by grid line convergence and mesh angle indicator function that smooth out the grid
- *providing a smooth boundary for the EGG:* by selectively inflating the boundary mesh in regions of high boundary curvature or at cusps

Grids of reasonable quality have been produced using this hybrid approach for a number of representative cases, with an example illustrated in Figures 1 – 4.

Figure 1: The thin boundary mesh generated by the HGG routine.

Figure 2: Complete hybrid mesh generated using HGG and EGG routines.

Figure 3: Detail of the pressure-side trailing edge hybrid mesh.

Figure 4: Detail of the suction-side leading edge hybrid mesh.

Grids for multiple passages are created by replicating the mesh vertically. Here periodic boundary conditions are again applied on the upper and lower edges of the combined mesh, with boundary conditions between blade passages switching between an imaginary boundary (where information is exchanged between passages) and non-slip boundaries at the solid walls.

RESULTS

1D RESULTS

To begin, a fully numerically-consistent 1D solver was created to model entropy noise generation due to simple linear acceleration effect. This model was validated against the canonical test case of the Entropy Wave Generator (EWG) [17], that has been used extensively as both a basis for validations of numerical codes and the development of entropy noise theory.

Figure 5: The EWG domain, showing the dimensions, the locations of the heat source and pressure transducer; 'mic 4' used to record the entropy noise signal.

The EWG computational domain, shown in Figure 5, is a 2350mm long duct consisting of

- A constant-area inlet duct: diameter 30mm, length 237mm
- A nozzle contraction: diameter 30mm contracting to 7.5mm, length 13mm
- A nozzle diffuser: diameter 7.5mm to 40mm, length 250mm
- A constant-area outlet duct: diameter 40mm, length 1850mm

The source is placed 100mm upstream of the nozzle throat, to match the location of the heating element in the experimental setup. Data is collected from a pressure probe at a location 1150mm downstream of the nozzle throat, matching the location of the fourth microphone used for the experimental analysis.

It has been shown by Lourier [18], that accurate modelling of the reflection properties at both the termination of the test section and the inlet are necessary in order to match the induced pressure disturbance accurately. The experiment itself attempts to create a non-reflecting exhaust by means of an anechoic expansion chamber attached to the end of the duct, however, it has been shown through extensive analysis that such a termination possesses reflecting characteristics equivalent to a first-order low-pass filter given in Equation 29.

$$R = \frac{-1}{1 - i(2\omega/K)}, \quad (29)$$

where K is the incoming wave coefficient defined by the NSCBCs as given in Equation 30.

$$K = \frac{\sigma a}{L}(1 - M^2). \quad (30)$$

Fortunately, the NSCBCs possess such a reflection factor, that may be tuned to match the required characteristics of the experimental boundary by changing σ . Lourier [18] has shown that better prediction of the pressure signal may be calculated by introducing so-called Time Domain Impedance Boundary Conditions (TDIBC). For the purposes of this work, however, it was decided to restrict the model to the present NSCBCs, due to the simplicity of the treatment. Two relaxation parameters of $\sigma = 1.8$ and $\sigma = 0.46$ were tested as per [19] and [20], where the higher relaxation corresponds to a more reflective condition.

Within the experimental set-up, entropy disturbances are generated by sequential triggering of heating wires upstream of the nozzle test section [17], though, in this simulation, a source is introduced directly on the entropy

characteristic. This means that the entropy forcing is not coupled with an associated acoustic wave, though a time-of-flight analysis conducted by Lourier [18] suggests that: a) the direct noise in this geometry is much lower in magnitude than the indirect noise and b) is detected prior to the arrival of the entropy noise disturbance. The forcing profile is modelled according to the form given by [20],

$$\Phi = \Phi_0 \zeta(t) \psi(x), \quad (31)$$

where $\zeta(t)$ accounts for the temporal variation and $\psi(x)$ the spatial distribution. Leyko proposed [20] that the temporal variation should be modelled by the exponential form in Equation 32,

$$\zeta(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t < t_s \\ 1 - e^{-\frac{t-t_s}{\tau}}, & \text{if } t_s \leq t \leq t_s + t_p \\ \zeta(t_s + t_p) e^{-\frac{t-t_s}{\tau}}, & \text{if } t \geq t_s + t_p \end{cases} \quad (32)$$

with the relaxation time $\tau = 3.5ms$ determined by minimising the least square error between the analytical and experimental data for the heat up period $t_s \leq t \leq t_s + t_p$ [21]. Duran [22] proposed a relaxation time $\tau = 7ms$, and this value is also tested.

The smoothness of the spatial distribution must be maintained in order to avoid spurious numerical oscillations in the region surrounding the source, as well as ensuring that the source term is differentiable for the linearization. To do this, a Gaussian form for $\psi(x)$ is taken, as in Equation 33 that localises the source, where κ is chosen so that the source is localised to 4-8 grid points.

$$\psi(x) = e^{-\frac{(x-x_0)^2}{2\kappa^2}}. \quad (33)$$

Figure 6: Acoustic response for both the experiment and numerical model at the fourth microphone generated by the entropy wave step function.

Figure 7: Parametric analysis of varying boundary and source relaxation parameters.

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show that the best fit for the relaxation parameters is achieved with $\sigma = 1.8$ and $\tau = 7ms$. Though the NSCBCs relaxation parameter is as expected, a larger relaxation time is used for the source. This may be due to 2D effects in the experiment that dissipate the wave prior to its interaction with the nozzle geometry.

This test case illustrates the importance of reflections when recovering the entropy noise acoustic signals and it is implied that, in 2D and 3D turbine geometries, the reflections of entropy noise from downstream boundaries or blade rows may have the potential to modify and introduce time-delayed feedback in the system.

2D RESULTS

The 2D model naturally extends the 1D duct form above by introducing an NGV blade row at the duct termination. This adds the additional 2D effects such as flow turning, vortex shedding, entropy wave distortion and tonal noise generation at the trailing edge, all of which are features of interest, that may interact non-trivially with the entropy waves and the generated noise.

Figure 8: Pressure coefficient (C_p) for the low-speed cascade validation at design conditions given in Table 1.

Figure 9: Pressure coefficient (C_p) for NASA-C3X geometry at off-design conditions as given in Table 1. The experimental data for this case considers a higher exit Mach number than is possible for the numerical solver due to a lack of shock capturing. Nevertheless a good match is obtained for the pressure coefficient.

The code described above is validated for a low-velocity linear cascade ([23], [24]), and the NASA C3X geometries ([25], [26]). The pressure coefficient C_p is computed around both aerofoils and compared with experimental data in Figure 8 and Figure 9, with conditions given in Table 1.

Table 1: A summary of the test conditions for the two validation cases used in the validation of the 2D code.

Test Case	Low speed cascade	NASA C3x (High speed cascade)
Inlet total pressure	107853Pa	244764Pa
Inlet total temperature	293.25K	802.00K
M_{exit}	0.3	0.85
Re	1×10^5	
Pr	0.71	
γ	1.4	

It is clear that an acceptable match is achieved in both the high and low-velocity validations cases, though it should be noted that in this solver turbulence modelling is not implemented, and so both cases are susceptible to separation near the trailing edge of the suction surface. Shock capturing is also outside the scope of this solver. Therefore, simulations at design conditions for the C3X geometry are not possible, since the flow reaches a maximum Mach number of 1.05 on the suction surface. This is reason for the slight deviation of the numerical results in the region close to the trailing edge.

For the remainder of this paper, the low-velocity cascade geometry is used. M_{exit} is increased to 0.44, in order to accelerate the flow at the duct inlet to $M = 0.05$; a modification necessary in order to increase the global time

step. A steady solution is calculated, with boundary layer separation being monitored at the trailing edge to ensure that this remains within acceptable limits. Then simulations are run until a quasi-steady solution is reached to ensure that no transient waves remain that could contaminate the solutions. At this point, a range of entropy forcing terms are added to quantify the generation of entropy noise and other behaviours under various forcing scenarios. The duct height function is chosen to give a contraction ratio of 3 between the computational boundary and the leading edge of the NGV. This is illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Duct height profile used for the low-velocity cascade test case.

The reference quantities for the non-dimensionalisation are taken at the outlet of the NGV and are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Reference quantities for 2D non-dimensionalisation.

Reference variable	Reference value
x_0	0.143 m
u_0	146.86 ms^{-1}
p_0	88927 Pa
s_0	$287.06 \text{ Jkg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$
M	0.4358

For the two-passage mesh, boundary conditions are applied as shown in Figure 11, with a non-slip boundary condition enforced along the section of the boundary representing the aerofoil (blue), periodic conditions on the upper and lower edges of the mesh not corresponding to the aerofoil (purple) and partially non-reflecting inflow/outflow boundary conditions of the type described above (green/red). The two sponge layers are placed in front of the inflow and outflow boundaries (hatched region) and entropy sources are placed at the duct inlet and at the leading edge of the NGV (yellow/orange region). Measurements are taken at the probes (a, b, c) and their images in the second passage (a', b', c'), corresponding to the leading edge, mid-chord and NGV exit respectively, shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11: Two-passage low-velocity cascade domain, illustrating the boundary conditions applied as well as the sponge layer and source locations.

Figure 12: Location of 'probes' (a, b, c) and their images (a', b', c') within the two-blade passage computational domain.

An initial flow field is computed in 2D without external entropy sources, providing an unperturbed reference case. Flow is accelerated from an inlet Mach number of 0.05 to an exit Mach number of 0.44, and strong vortex shedding is observed from the trailing edge region in Figure 13, with a non-dimensional shedding frequency of $f_{vs} = 8.5$ (8.73kHz). The corresponding tonal noise signature in both the time-domain pressure signal and its frequency decomposition are shown in Figure 14 and Figure 15.

Figure 13: Unperturbed case: entropy field snapshot showing unmodified trailing-edge vortex shedding.

Figure 14: Unperturbed case: pressure trace at location c and c' (at NGV exit). Steady vortex shedding at constant frequency is observed.

Figure 15: Unperturbed case: showing trailing edge noise localised to a non-dimensional frequency of $f_{vs} = 8.5$ (corresponding to 8730Hz).

A pure sinusoidal plane-wave entropy packet is then propagated from the source at the yellow region in Figure 9 corresponding to temperature fluctuations of 10% of inlet total temperature at a frequency of $f_{source} = 0.133$

(137Hz), representative of a combustor instability. A snapshot of the resulting entropy field is shown in Figure 16, with the increase in vortex shedding strength shown clearly when compared to the unperturbed case in Figure 13.

Figure 16: Low-frequency entropy perturbation case: entropy field snapshot showing the passage of low-frequency entropy disturbances through the blade passage. Entropy wave frequency is 0.13 (equivalent to 137Hz).

The time-series plot of the entropy signal in the upper and lower passages correlates well with the new pressure fluctuations observed at the NGV exit in Figure 17, confirming that entropy noise has been generated.

Figure 17: Low-frequency entropy perturbation case: pressure trace at the trailing edge (location c) showing the superposition of the entropy noise and vortex shedding noise. The time is taken between $t=20$ and $t=50$ to capture four entropy wave cycles.

In addition to the superposition effect shown in Figure 17, a closeup of the waveform in Figure 18 shows the modulation of the vortex shedding pattern as a result of an interaction between the entropy wave and the vortex shedding mechanism, as seen with the varying amplitude of the pressure signal at locations A and B in Figure 18.

Figure 18: Low-frequency entropy perturbation case: detail of the pressure trace shown in Figure 14 between $t=42$ and $t=52$, showing the modulation to the trailing edge noise as a result of the interaction with the entropy wave. It is clear to see that the amplitude of the vortex shedding is modulated when comparing the amplitude within areas A and B.

Moreover, Fourier transforms of the pressure field at these locations, in Figure 19, clearly show a new peak at the entropy noise/forcing frequency, and an increase in the shedding strength/tonal noise by approximately one-third of the unperturbed case. It is observed in Figure 20 that, in the vicinity of the vortex shedding frequency, another peak is present at a frequency $f_{sp} = f_{vs} - f_{source}$, 1/4 of the magnitude the trailing edge noise. The trailing edge frequency is also reduced to 8.448 (8676Hz), suggesting that an interaction exists between the entropy wave and the trailing edge vortex shedding, though for the present test case it seems to be insignificant.

Figure 19: Low-frequency entropy perturbation case: showing the additional low-frequency peak in the pressure transform due to entropy noise generation in the duct and through the blade row.

Figure 20: Low-frequency entropy perturbation case: showing the appearance of additional peaks at integer multiples of f_{source} either side of f_{vs} . The frequency gap to the largest of these peaks is illustrated here.

Setting $f_{source} = 0.85$ (880Hz), entropy waves with a frequency more representative of the blade-passing frequency are introduced, and an instantaneous snapshot of the entropy field is illustrated in Figure 21. The input amplitude of the entropy wave is 5% of total temperature due to the response characteristics of the source at the higher frequencies.

Figure 21: High-frequency entropy perturbation case: entropy field snapshot. The frequency of the forcing is 0.85 (880Hz).

Frequency decompositions of this field in Figure 22 confirm a similar behaviour as in the low-frequency case, with two peaks appearing either side of f_{vs} , with the frequency gap equal to that of the forcing frequency. As with the previous case, a slight deviation occurs to f_{vs} , with a change to 8.464 (8693Hz). This is again not clear enough to suggest a presence of synchronisation phenomenon between the vortex shedding and the entropy wave forcing. It is interesting to note that despite the 50% reduction in source strength, the resulting entropy noise is reduced by 12 times when compared to the low-frequency case, showing a significant preference of the entropy noise mechanism to the lower frequencies. Moreover, the secondary peak at f_{sp} does not vary proportionately to the reduction in entropy

noise, suggesting a more complex mechanism than a simple linear relationship between it and the source strength.

Figure 22: High frequency entropy perturbation case: illustrating the secondary peak adjacent to the vortex-shedding frequency, at a distance f_{source} from the vortex-shedding noise at f_{vs} .

Finally, an example with the entropy field perturbed at the NGV inlet is given in Figure 23. Entropy disturbances are applied at the yellow region of Figure 12, and illustrates how features in the flow may be isolated from parts of the geometry upstream from the source. The wavefronts in this case are angled at $\pi/3$ relative to the axial coordinate axis, which forces one of the passages in antiphase to the other. As a result, the two trailing edge wakes experience opposing forcing. Despite this distortion to the inlet wave, it is not clear from the acoustic spectrum in Figure 24 that any qualitative features beyond those observed in the previous examples are present in this case, though again it should be noted that a secondary peak appears at f_{sp} , and its magnitude appears to be independent of the entropy noise signature, the distortion of the incoming waves and the source position.

Figure 23: Distorted wavefronts at NGV case: Wavefronts in this case are oriented $\pi/3$ to the axial coordinate axis to provide a forcing that is in antiphase within the two blade rows.

Figure 24: Distorted entropy perturbation wavefronts at NGV case: showing the secondary peak as observed in the low-frequency and high-frequency cases.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Interest in reducing aviation noise is prompting the re-examination of previously insignificant acoustic sources in turbomachinery. The analysis of entropy noise, in particular, requires a unified model capable of simultaneously simulating generation and propagation through turbine duct and blade row geometries. This is a problem that is commonly analysed with significant simplifications or using low-order CFD codes that are unable to propagate accurately acoustic disturbances.

A distinctive high-order, characteristics-based computational aeroacoustics code, with non-linear, linearized and adjoint components was described and modified for the analysis of turbomachinery acoustics problems. Appropriate boundary conditions were discussed and, duct term modifications introduced to the Navier-Stokes equations to represent the varying streamtube height upstream of the blade row. A numerically consistent 1D code was used to validate the entropy noise generation and propagation capabilities against established experimental data, showing good agreement, and a parametric analysis of the downstream reflection characteristics was performed. Calculations of the pressure coefficients for 2D aerofoils in both low-speed and high-speed cases showed good agreement with experimental data.

A 2D linear cascade with two blade passages was described, and a steady solution showing 2D vortex shedding was obtained. The flow field and the trailing-edge vortex shedding noise were then analysed in the vicinity of the trailing edge for a high and low-frequency plane entropy wave introduced at the domain inlet, and an angled wave was created in front of the leading edge of the nozzle guide vane. A brief analysis showed an increase in vortex shedding strength for all entropy source cases, and the formation of a secondary peak at a frequency $f_{sp} = f_{vs} - f_{source}$ was observed. Modulation of the vortex shedding strength was also noted in the pressure signal.

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